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Research Article

STUDY TO KNOW THE SERUM ZINC, MAGNESIUM AND CHROMIUM LEVELS IN TYPE II DIABETIC PATIENTS

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Abstract:

Objective: To investigate the relationship between trace element deficiency and diabetes mellitus.

Study Design: A prospective, comparative and cross sectional study.

Place and Duration: In the Endocrinology department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for Six Months duration from November 2018 to April 2019.

Materials and Methods: In this study, 100 total patients were included, fifty patients of type 2 diabetes and fifty normal healthy subjects. The study was held in the Endocrinology department of the Mayo Hospital and from their relatives normal healthy individuals were selected. It was a constant analysis and prerequisite samples were taken from the patients of diabetes mellitus and healthy normal subjects for six months. By glucose oxidase method; Plasma glucose level was determined. The modified colorimetric method of Winterhalter and Fluckiger was used to estimate HbA1c levels. By atomic absorption spectrophotometer; Serum trace elements were calculated.

Results: In diabetic patients; Fasting blood glucose level was higher significantly (150.98 ± 37.980) mg / dL than healthy non-diabetic controls (87.920 ± 9.71 mg / dl). In diabetic patients; the mean HbA1-c level was higher than that of non-diabetic healthy controls ($7.470 \pm 1.183\%$ by weight) (5.664 ± 0.0747 mg). There was no statistically significant variation in mean Cu ++ level in diabetic patients (88.4 ± 40 μ g / dl) and 101 ± 39 μ g / dl in normal healthy controls (P value > 0.05). Serum Zn was significantly lower in diabetics (510 ± 89 μ g / dl) than in diabetic patients (603 ± 91 μ g / dl) (P value < 0.05). Similarly, in diabetics; serum chromium level was lower significantly (2.09 ± 0.9 μ g / dl) than in normal healthy controls (2.61 ± 0.054 μ g / dl). In diabetics; the mean serum Mg + + level was lower significantly (17.76 ± 0.66 / g / dl) than (22.13 ± 1.65 μ g) in normal healthy controls with 0.05 P value.

Conclusion: In this study, magnesium, zinc and chromium in serum were lower significantly in diabetics compared to normal healthy subjects. The serum copper was also low, but not significant statistically.

Key words: Diabetes, Trace element, glycosylated Haemoglobin.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic condition of carbohydrate, protein and lipid metabolism. There is an incorrect or incomplete response from the insulin secretion, which results in incomplete metabolism of carbohydrates [1]. The hyperglycemia is a characteristic feature of diabetes mellitus. The most common non-communicable disease is diabetes which affect approximately 100 million people [2]. In Pakistan; 6.9 million People are suffered by diabetes mellitus. The IDF estimates that by 2025, this number increases up to 11.5 million unless actions are taken to combat the disease [3]. Once, Type 2 diabetes mellitus was measured as uncommon disease, but recently there has been fast rise in its frequency [4]. Hyperinsulinemia and Insulin resistance are characteristic of both impaired glucose tolerance and type 2 diabetes mellitus. In medical research, the importance of trace elements has raised in current years. For humans, many trace elements are necessary and many metabolic developments depend on regular trace element concentrations. In various diseases, deficiency occurred such as anaemia, diabetes, aging, depression and heart disease. DM is a heterogeneous disease characterized by relative or absolute deficit of insulin and resistance to insulin. Various authors have determined the status and levels of minerals in diabetic subjects, but frequently conflicting and inconsistent results are accessible (often to a point that is not valid) [5]. This variation may be because of the subject's number, gender, and laboratory procedures. Various trace elements serve as antioxidants and prevent the membrane peroxidation [6]. Others have effect on glucose metabolism directly. The main copper transport protein in plasma, ceruloplasmin has a strong antioxidant property [7]. Manganese is a cofactor for various enzyme systems including arginine found to rise in animals having diabetes mellitus such as in mice and rats. Magnesium plays a key role as a cofactor in glucose phosphorylation and various other reactions of enzymes [8]. For normal metabolism of lipids and carbohydrates in mammals; Chromium serves as component of glucose tolerance factor (GTF). The insulin receptor acts by activating the activity of the kinase up to seven-fold, thereby increasing self-amplification and insulin efficiency [8]. On the other hand, Magnesium acts as a cofactor for the glycolytic pathway of certain enzymes and increases the insulin ability to stimulate tyrosine kinase. Zinc (Zn) is an important micronutrient that have significant role in the various enzymes proper functioning in metabolism of insulin and serve as an effective antioxidant [9]. Zn is important for metabolic diseases (diabetes, insulin resistance, metabolic syndrome) because it has an important role in the insulin hexamers stabilization,

the hormone in the pancreas storage and is an effective antioxidant [10]. Oxidative stress is considered as a significant factor. Insulin resistance and component in the onset and progression of diabetes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This is a prospective, comparative and cross-sectional study in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients compared to normal healthy subjects in the Endocrinology department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for Six Months duration from November 2018 to April 2019. 100 total subjects were included, 50 with type 2 diabetes mellitus and fifty normal healthy subjects. The study was held in the Endocrinology department of the Services Hospital and from their relatives normal healthy individuals were selected. It was a constant analysis and prerequisite samples were taken from the patients of diabetes mellitus and healthy normal subjects for six months. After written consent, Subjects were included and detailed evaluation and examination was done. Patients having endocrine disorders, liver disorders and kidney diseases or taking other drugs were not included and for women, pregnant women and those using OCPS were also not included. Both normal healthy subjects and patients were asked to participate in fasting for 10 to 12 hours for blood glucose fasting level and 2 hours after breakfast (2HABF). Samples were taken after breakfast to determine blood sugar, serum Cu, Cr, Mg, glycosylated haemoglobin and Zn levels. To estimate blood glucose levels on an empty stomach 1.5 ml of blood was collected aseptically in a 5 cc disposable syringe. Two hours after breakfast, seven ml of a 2nd blood sample was taken in a 10 cc syringe to determine 2HABF (blood glucose level), serum trace element and HbA 1-c levels. For the prediction of HbA 1-c, three ml were placed in the EDTA tube, in a second test tube, 4 ml blood was held and certified to clot to determine trace and glucose elements. At 2000 rpm; coagulated blood was centrifuged in the test tube for 3 minutes and the serum was stored and separated at -200 ° C until transferred to the laboratory for biochemical examination. Using the glucose oxidase method; Plasma glucose level was determined. The improved colorimetric procedure of Winterhalter and Fluckiger was used to estimate HbA1c levels. By atomic absorption spectrophotometer; Serum trace elements were calculated.

RESULTS:

Among the 2 groups, all diabetic patients were married, male were 40% and female were 60%. From 40% males, 64% were smokers and 30% did not smoke. Of those without diabetes, 10% were single, 90% married, 50% male, and 50% female. Of the 50%

of men, 76% did not smoke and 24% smoked. 24% of diabetic patients used Biguanides, 70% sulfonyluria and insulin in combination with oral hypoglycemic

agents were taking 6%. The height, age, BMI and weight of the 2 groups are given in the table (1).

Table 1: Descriptive of age, height weight and BMI of diabetics and non diabetics P value less than 0.05 is significant

Variable	Diabetics (n=50)		Non diabetics (n=50)		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Age –years	43.26	2.912	43.36	3.306	0.245
Height –cm	155.820	11.272	159.73	10.102	0.677
Weight – kg	71.12	8.665	72.10	13.452	0.001
BMI	29.59	4.702	27.671	6.241	0.257

43.26 ± 2,912 was the mean age of diabetic patients was and 43.36 ± 3,306 for healthy non-diabetic controls. Without significance, > 0.05 was the P value. The diabetics mean height was lower (155 ± 20, 11.272 cm) than non-diabetic patients (160 ± 10,102 cm) and p value greater than 0.05 was not significant. For the diabetic group; 71.120 ± 13.452 Kg was the mean weight and for the non-diabetic healthy control

72.10 ± 13.452 Kg and > 0.05 P value. In diabetic patients (29 ± 4.702) Body mass index (BMI) was higher significantly than in the healthy control group without diabetes (27.671 ± 0.257) and P <0.05. In diabetic patients; mean fasting blood glucose level was higher significantly than in healthy controls non-diabetic (87.99 ± 9.69mg / dl) (Table 2) (P value <0.05) (150.39 ± 38.10 mg / dl).

Table 2: Descriptive of fasting blood glucose level and Hb A1-c in diabetics and non diabetics P value less 0.05 is significant

Variables	Diabetics (n=50)		Non diabetics (n=50)		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Fasting blood glucose level mg/dl	151.38	37.970	88.320	9.97-	<0.05
Hb A 1-c	7.470	1.183	5.664	0.747	<0.05

In mean Cu ++ level; there was no significant statistically variation in diabetic patients (88.4 ± 40 µg / dl) and normal healthy controls (101 ± 39 µg / dl) (P value > 0.05). (Table 3). In diabetic patients; Serum Zn

was lower significantly (510 ± 89 µg / dl) than in healthy subjects (603 ± 91µg / dl) (P value less than 0.05) (Table 3).

Table 3 : descriptive of serum Cu, Zn, Cr and Mg levels in diabetics and non diabetics healthy controls (P value less than 0.05 is significant)

Trace element	Normal healthy controls	Patients with diabetes type 2	P Value
Copper	101 ±39	88.4±40	0.1
Zinc	603±91	510.4±89	0.001
Chromium	2.61±0.054	1.99±0.8	0.001
Magnesium	22.13±1.65	17.76±0.66	0.005

Similarly, in diabetics serum chromium levels were lower significantly (1.99 ± 0.8 µg / dl) compared to normal healthy controls (2.61 ± 0.054 / g / dl) (P value <0.05) (Table 3). In diabetics; the mean serum Mg ++ level was lower significantly (17.76 ± 0.66 / g / dl) than in normal healthy subjects (22.13 ± 1.65 µg) (P value <0.05).

In the review of clinical studies published in recent years, it is clear that several minerals are of great importance and have a potential impact on typical diabetes patients [11]. The most common minerals of concern in diabetic patients are magnesium, zinc, chromium and copper. A change in the state of trace elements has been reported in various disease states, traumas and infections. It is known that liver and kidney diseases affect tissue distribution and excretion

DISCUSSION:

of trace elements. Excessive deposition or depletion of trace elements may have significant clinical effects, such as increased risk of cancer, cardiovascular disease, anemia of immunodeficiency, renal failure and bone disease [12]. The actual state of these elements in diabetes and other diseases is not yet clear. A number of signs and symptoms of diabetes are shared by different deficiencies of trace elements [13]. These include impaired glucose tolerance, fasting hyperglycemia, glycosuria, hypoglycemia, high circulating insulin, nephropathy, and peripheral neuropathy. Fasting blood glucose and glycosylated hemoglobin levels were significantly higher in diabetics compared to healthy non-diabetic controls. Anetor et al. In 2002, fasting plasma glucose and glycosylated hemoglobin levels were found to be high in diabetic patients [13]. In the diabetic group, serum chromium levels were significantly lower than those of normal non-diabetic controls who confirmed the findings of Nouramonamadi et al 2000, which reported a lower serum chromium level in diabetics [14]. Ding et al. 1998 also reported significantly lower serum chromium levels in elderly diabetics. Davis et al. 1997/25 also reported a decrease in chromium levels in patients with type 2 diabetes. In this study, serum zinc levels in patients with type 2 diabetes were lower than in normal healthy subjects [15]. It has been suggested that the decrease in serum zinc levels is due to the formation of insulin complexes and therefore free insulin deficiency improves the appearance of diabetes symptoms in these patients.

CONCLUSION:

Serum magnesium, Zn and chromium levels were lower in Type 2 diabetics than normal healthy controls, but serum copper levels were lower but not important. To better know the importance of these trace elements in diabetes, additional clinical trials involving more patients and more sophisticated methods are needed. Urine samples, hair and blood should also be taken to clarify the image.

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